

STUDIES IN THE COMPOSITION OF FERRIC ARSENITE AND FERROUS
ARSENATE. PART I. QUALITATIVE STUDY OF THE REACTION
BETWEEN FERRIC CHLORIDE AND SODIUM ARSENITE

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By reacting ferric chloride with sodium arsenite in aqueous and neutralised and acidified solutions interesting evidences have been obtained of intermediate reactions between the reactants. The most important factors which govern the composition of ferric arsenite are : (i) the oxidation-reduction phenomenon between the reactants, (ii) H-ion concentration of the system, (iii) hydrolytic character of the compound, and (iv) the phenomenon of adsorption.

The composition of ferric arsenite according to the chemical equation should correspond to the formula $\text{Fe}(\text{AsO}_2)_3$ when FeCl_3 is added to NaAsO_2 . But in the literature more complex and variable formulae have been given e.g. $6\text{K}_2\text{O}, 5\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3, 9\text{As}_2\text{O}_3, 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Dobbin, *Pharm. J.*, 1904, *iv*, 81, 588), $\text{XFe}(\text{OH})_3, \text{YAs}_2\text{O}_3$ (Oryng, *Kolloid Z.*, 1918, 22, 149; and $\text{Fe}_4\text{As}_2\text{O}_{15}, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $3\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3, \text{Fe}_2(\text{AsO}_3)_2, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Bunsen and Berthold : Mellor, "Treatise on Inorganic Chemistry", 1929, Vol. IX, p. 133).

The possibility of mutual oxidation and reduction was, however, suggested by Jellinek and Winogradoff (*Z. Electrochem.*, 1924, 30, 477) according to the following equation,

The above possibility of mutual oxidation and reduction suggests that the composition of ferric arsenite will be more or less a mixed compound. The secondary reactions which may follow may be indicated at a first glance as given below :

- (i) $2\text{FeCl}_3 + \text{NaAsO}_2 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow 2\text{FeCl}_2 + \text{NaCl} + \text{HCl} + \text{H}_3\text{AsO}_4$
- (ii) $3\text{FeCl}_2 + 2\text{H}_3\text{AsO}_4 \rightarrow \text{Fe}_3(\text{AsO}_4)_2 + 6\text{HCl}$
- (iii) $\text{FeCl}_3 + \text{H}_3\text{AsO}_4 \rightarrow \text{FeAsO}_4 + 3\text{HCl}$
- and (iv) $\text{FeCl}_2 + 2\text{NaAsO}_2 \rightarrow \text{Fe}(\text{AsO}_2)_2 + 2\text{NaCl}.$

The ionic equation showing the oxidation-reduction products may be represented thus :

In order to study the above possibilities a number of samples of ferric arsenite was prepared by mixing the aqueous neutralised and slightly acidified solutions of the reactants and the filtrate was thoroughly subjected to qualitative analysis in each case.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

1. Aqueous solutions of ferric chloride and sodium arsenite ($M/5$, $M/10$, $M/25$ and $M/50$) were prepared and mixed together in equivalent proportion. The filtrates were collected and tested. It was observed that the filtrates were neutral: ferrous and ferric, nil, and arsenite was left over in excess, but no arsenate.

2. Aqueous solutions of ferric chloride and neutralised solutions of sodium arsenite, both at the above concentrations, were mixed in equivalent proportion (1 mole of FeCl_3 to 3 moles of NaAsO_2). The filtrate was acidic, ferrous and ferric were both present, arsenite was in excess but arsenate was doubtful.

A few more interesting points regarding the precipitation of ferric arsenite were noted, according as the solutions were aqueous, neutralised sodium arsenite or acidic.

3. When aqueous solutions of FeCl_3 or NaAsO_2 were mixed together, sufficient $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ was precipitated along with ferric arsenite, because of the free alkali in NaAsO_2 solution. The precipitation was immediate and deep brown in colour.

4. When aqueous solution of ferric chloride was mixed with neutralised solution of NaAsO_2 , a colloidal solution of ferric arsenite was first formed, which precipitated on keeping overnight. A brown supernatant layer of colloidal $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ mixed with ferric arsenite was also observed.

5. When more than one equivalent of aqueous or acidified solution of ferric chloride was added to one equivalent of aqueous or neutralised solution of NaAsO_2 , a colloidal solution of ferric arsenite was first formed which precipitated gradually in a short time.

6. Several samples of ferric arsenite were prepared by mixing excess of acidified ferric chloride to neutralised NaAsO_2 . A colloidal solution was obtained. This was dialysed in a parchment paper bag and the dialysate was concentrated. The dialysate showed that both ferrous and arsenate ions were present.

After these preliminary qualitative tests quantitative estimations were made to find out whether the same amount of residual arsenite was left over, when the reactants were mixed in equivalent proportion, but at different dilutions. This would show the effect of hydrolysis on ferric arsenite.

TABLE I

Conc. of the reactants.	Initial amount. of AsO_2 .	Amount. of AsO_2 left over.	Amount. of AsO_2 used up by FeCl_3 .
1. $M/1.3\text{-FeCl}_3 + M/1.3\text{-NaAsO}_2$	0.4253 g.	0.2341 g.	0.2012 g.
2. $M/5 + M/5$	0.4253	0.2352	0.190
3. $M/10 + M/10$	0.4253	0.2402	0.1861
4. $M/25 + M/25$	0.4253	0.2604	0.1649
5. $M/50 + M/50$	0.4253	0.2882	0.1371

DISCUSSION

The qualitative results show that mutual oxidation and reduction of the reactants do take place when neutralised or acidified solutions are mixed together. Another interesting point to note is that the aqueous solutions of ferric chloride and sodium arsenite, on mixing, give a neutral filtrate, although taken separately, FeCl_3 is acidic and NaAsO_2 is strongly alkaline. The residual AsO_2 in the filtrate shows that the total quantity of ferric chloride is not utilised in forming ferric arsenite, probably due to (i) the formation of intermediate products by mutual oxidation and reduction of the reactants, and (ii) hydrolysis of ferric arsenite, an indication of which has been obtained quantitatively in the above table.

The mechanism of the reactions between the aqueous solutions of ferric chloride and sodium arsenite therefore does not seem to be only a one-stage process. It appears that there are several intermediate reactions which have been shown in the equations given below:

The foregoing scheme of chemical changes covers the range of observation made qualitatively in the case of aqueous solutions. The resultant equation shows that (a) there is no free acid or alkali, (b) there is enough of free HAsO_2 in the solution, and (c) ferric arsenite hydrolyses more in dilute solutions, with proportionate increase in free HAsO_2 as already observed.

But when neutralised NaAsO_2 is mixed with FeCl_3 , the chemical changes probably take place according to the following modifications:

The above scheme of reactions suggests that the required proportion of ferric chloride to sodium arsenite (neutralised) is 7:6. Hence, when FeCl_3 is added to NaAsO_2 in equivalent proportion *i. e.* in the ratio of 1:3, excess of ferric and ferrous ions will appear in the filtrate and this has actually been observed (*vide* experimental 2). Test for arsenate is readily obtained, but the formation of arsenate is favoured by adding an excess of acidified FeCl_3 (*vide* experimental 6).

In view of the observations made by qualitative analysis of the filtrates obtained by mixing ferric chloride and sodium arsenite under different conditions of H-ion concentration and dilution, it may be concluded that the mechanism of reaction is complicated by intermediate changes brought about by mutual oxidation and reduction, hydrolysis of the products formed and by adsorption. Quantitative analysis of the various samples of ferric arsenite prepared will be communicated in a future communication.

The author owes his thanks to Dr. N. R. Dhar and Dr. S. Ghosh of Allahabad University and to Dr. S. S. Deshapande of Agra College for the interest they took in these investigations.

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Received June 23, 1947.